

A Comprehensive Survey on Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication (URLLC) in Non-Terrestrial Networks

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Abstract

Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication (URLLC) is a cornerstone of mission-critical applications in next-generation wireless networks. While significant advancements have been made in terrestrial deployments, the integration of URLLC with Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs), including satellites, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), and High Altitude Platform Systems (HAPS), is emerging as a pivotal area of research. NTNs extend connectivity to underserved and remote regions, unlocking new possibilities in industrial automation, telemedicine, disaster recovery, and beyond. This survey provides a thorough analysis of URLLC in NTNs, systematically categorizing state-of-the-art research, highlighting key challenges, and outlining future research directions. Topics covered include latency challenges, spectrum sharing and resource allocation, integration with terrestrial networks, and the utilization of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS).

Index Terms

URLLC, Non-Terrestrial Networks, Satellite Communications, UAVs, HAPS, 6G Networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication (URLLC) is a cornerstone of 5G and beyond, specifically engineered to address the stringent demands of latency and reliability for mission-critical applications. These include autonomous vehicles, where real-time communication ensures safety and navigation, remote surgeries that demand precision and instantaneous feedback, and industrial automation enabling synchronized operation of robotics and machinery. Traditionally, research on URLLC has primarily concentrated on terrestrial networks, focusing on enhancing the existing infrastructure to meet these requirements [1]–[5]. However, as the demands for ubiquitous connectivity and global reach intensify, the integration of URLLC with Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs) is rapidly emerging as a critical domain of interest. NTNs, comprising satellite systems, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), and High Altitude Platform Systems (HAPS), provide unparalleled advantages such as global coverage, rapid deployment capabilities, and resilience against physical infrastructure failure. These characteristics make NTNs indispensable for applications in geographically isolated regions, disaster-stricken zones, and areas lacking robust terrestrial infrastructure. Their potential becomes especially transformative when integrated with URLLC, as this synergy facilitates a broad range of critical applications. These include disaster recovery operations that require immediate communication capabilities, telemedicine services for remote and underserved regions, and the deployment of global Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) networks to optimize industrial processes on a worldwide scale [6], [7].

Despite these benefits, NTNs exhibit unique characteristics that present significant challenges for the implementation of URLLC. High propagation delays, a fundamental issue in satellite communications, hinder the ability to meet stringent sub-millisecond latency requirements. Limited bandwidth availability in NTNs, coupled with increased demand for reliable and efficient data transmission, creates a bottleneck that must be addressed through advanced spectrum-sharing mechanisms. Furthermore, the highly variable and dynamic nature of NTN channel conditions adds complexity to maintaining consistent communication quality and reliability [8]. Overcoming these challenges requires innovative solutions across multiple dimensions. On the hardware front, advancements in low-power, high-performance transceivers and phased-array

antennas are crucial. At the protocol level, dynamic resource allocation strategies, hybrid communication architectures, and latency-aware routing algorithms are emerging as key enablers. System-level designs must incorporate cutting-edge technologies, such as AI and machine learning, to optimize resource usage and predictively adapt to environmental changes. Moreover, the integration of edge computing nodes within NTN significantly reduces latency by processing data closer to end-users. In addition, the fusion of NTN with terrestrial networks introduces opportunities to create hybrid systems that leverage the strengths of both domains. Seamless interoperability between NTN and terrestrial infrastructure can be achieved through advanced handover mechanisms, network slicing for URLLC traffic prioritization, and collaborative spectrum management.

This paper provides an extensive and detailed overview of the advancements and challenges associated with integrating URLLC with NTN. The primary objective of this work is to establish a foundational understanding of the current landscape while identifying critical areas for further research. Firstly, the paper categorizes the vast body of existing research based on application domains and technological advancements. This includes examining the utilization of URLLC-NTN systems across fields such as satellite communications, UAVs, and HAPS. The aim is to provide a comprehensive framework to understand how different technologies and applications intersect within this domain. Secondly, it highlights key challenges that hinder the seamless integration of URLLC with NTN. Among the most pressing issues are latency optimization, resource allocation, and security. These challenges are deeply analyzed to uncover underlying factors, such as propagation delays, limited spectrum resources, and evolving cyber threats, that complicate their resolution. Lastly, the paper identifies future directions and emerging trends of URLLC-NTN integration. Notable among these are AI-driven optimization techniques, which hold immense promise in enhancing resource allocation and network efficiency, and the adoption of Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) to dynamically improve signal quality and coverage.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature on the integration of URLLC with NTN can be categorized into three primary categories: satellite-based URLLC, UAV-enabled URLLC, and HAPS.

A. *Satellite-Based URLLC*

Satellites play a pivotal role in providing ubiquitous connectivity, making them essential for critical applications in remote and underserved areas, as well as global logistics. Their unique ability to offer wide-area coverage makes them indispensable for bridging the digital divide and supporting advanced communication needs. However, one of the primary challenges in satellite networks is the mitigation of latency, a key requirement for URLLC. Research in this domain has focused on leveraging multi-orbit constellations, including low Earth orbit (LEO) satellites, which significantly reduce propagation delays compared to geostationary satellites. Additionally, integrating edge processing capabilities onboard satellites minimizes end-to-end latency by processing data closer to its origin, thus enabling faster decision-making and communication. In terms of reliability, satellites contribute through redundant communication paths and the development of hybrid satellite-terrestrial architectures. These systems ensure consistent performance even in adverse conditions or in the event of partial network failures. Advanced error correction codes have also been instrumental in maintaining high levels of reliability, meeting the stringent demands of URLLC applications such as telemedicine and autonomous systems. Spectrum efficiency is another critical area where satellite technologies excel. By employing dynamic spectrum sharing techniques, satellites can coexist with terrestrial networks, optimizing the use of limited frequency resources. AI-based algorithms and cooperative spectrum sensing further enhance this efficiency by dynamically adapting to network conditions and reducing interference. Emerging applications driven by satellite capabilities are also gaining momentum. Notable examples include satellite-enabled immersive experiences, such as holographic communication and real-time digital twins. These applications are transforming industries

by providing unprecedented levels of interaction and insight, making satellites a cornerstone for next-generation connectivity solutions.

The study in [9] focuses on optimizing URLLC in next-generation 6G networks through the integration of satellite and terrestrial systems. The proposed traffic offloading mechanism prioritizes URLLC traffic by assigning it to terrestrial networks, ensuring compliance with its stringent latency requirements. Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) traffic, which is less delay-sensitive, is allocated to satellites, thereby optimizing the overall system. The results highlight that this strategy significantly reduces URLLC transmission delays and improves network availability by effectively managing the high traffic load. The work in [10] explores the structured integration of satellites, UAVs, and terrestrial networks to address the limitations of 5G networks and meet the demands of 6G communication systems. It emphasizes extending connectivity to space, air, and maritime regions, ensuring universal coverage for diverse applications, including the intelligent Internet of Things (IoT). The paper highlights the inherent trade-offs between latency, reliability, and coverage in hybrid space-air-ground networks. Satellites provide wide coverage but face latency challenges, UAVs offer mobility and proximity but require complex management, and terrestrial base stations deliver low latency but are geographically constrained. To address these complexities, the study proposes a hierarchical network structure and an on-demand coverage optimization method. This approach enhances URLLC performance by ensuring low latency and high reliability for applications like autonomous robotics and industrial automation, even in remote or underserved areas.

The study in [11] investigates the integration of digital twin (DT) technology into NTN, which include both airborne and space-borne elements. NTN face significant challenges in network control, management, and optimization due to their dynamic and complex nature. DT technology offers a transformative approach by providing virtual representations of NTN ecosystems, enabling real-time monitoring, simulations, and data-driven decision-making. A key focus is on enhancing performance for use cases such as URLLC and eMBB. The paper presents a case study demonstrating a data-driven DT model for dynamic network slicing within an open radio access network (O-RAN) architecture. This model optimizes resources for both URLLC and eMBB, addressing the stringent latency and reliability requirements of URLLC while ensuring efficient eMBB performance. The work in [12] focuses on ensuring reliable communication connectivity for aerial vehicles (AVs), such as electric vertical take-off and landing (eVTOL) aircraft, to support safe and scalable operations in urban environments. The authors propose a multi-connectivity enabled aerial network incorporating vertical heterogeneous networks, including direct air-to-ground, air-to-air communication, HAPS, and LEO satellites. The study emphasizes the stringent requirements of URLLC for command and control services. By analyzing end-to-end reliability and latency under the finite blocklength regime, the paper evaluates various multi-connectivity configurations to meet these demanding connectivity needs. Challenges such as line-of-sight interference and reduced gains of downtilt ground base station antennas are addressed through coordinated multi-point (CoMP) techniques to mitigate inter-cell interference. Additionally, the authors solve an optimization problem to select the optimal path, maximizing spectral efficiency and minimizing the number of required links.

B. UAV-enabled URLLC

UAVs are emerging as highly agile communication relays, proving to be particularly valuable in scenarios such as disaster recovery and the establishment of dynamic IoT networks. Their flexibility and mobility allow them to be rapidly deployed to areas where terrestrial communication infrastructure may be damaged or insufficient. UAV trajectory optimization plays a crucial role in ensuring that these aerial systems provide maximum coverage and minimal latency [13]. By carefully planning their flight paths, UAVs can serve as highly efficient relays, connecting isolated nodes and users. Additionally, swarm coordination techniques enable multiple UAVs to operate in unison, distributing communication loads intelligently and enhancing the overall network performance.

The study in [14] explores the joint optimization of blocklength resource allocation and UAV trajectory for URLLC in a UAV relay wireless communication system. Utilizing the decode-and-forward protocol, the

UAV acts as a relay to facilitate communication between a ground base station and multiple ground users. The paper focuses on maximizing the end-to-end information rate by optimizing the blocklengths and UAV trajectory while adhering to constraints related to finite blocklengths and UAV flight limitations. This study tackles the complex non-convex optimization problem by integrating successive convex approximation, relaxation, and integerization techniques to achieve a practical and effective solution. The work in [15] investigates the use of UAVs to support URLLC by leveraging their capability to establish high-probability Line-of-Sight links. The paper introduces a trajectory planning framework that balances energy efficiency during dynamic UAV flight with stringent communication quality requirements. The authors introduced a LoS persistence-based motion prediction method and a path exploration technique that optimizes D2D communication quality while forming optimal network topologies. Additionally, the framework employs a trajectory optimization method to generate spatio-temporally efficient flight paths within predefined corridors, ensuring optimal LoS link quality and safety.

The study in [16] introduces a framework for deploying UAVs to deliver critical URLLC services in out-of-coverage areas. The paper focuses on optimizing resource allocation, including resource blocks and power allocation, as well as determining optimal UAV deployment strategies for UAV-assisted 5G networks. The goal is to jointly maximize the average sum-rate while minimizing UAV transmit power, all while meeting strict URLLC requirements. To address the sporadic nature of URLLC traffic, the study proposes an online traffic prediction model using Gaussian Process Regression (GPR). This model facilitates optimal scheduling and power allocation for URLLC services. The formulated optimization problem is solved using a successive minimization algorithm. The work in [17] focuses on optimizing UAV-enabled relay systems for delivering command information under URLLC constraints. The primary objective is to jointly optimize blocklength allocation and UAV positioning to minimize decoding error probability while meeting strict latency requirements. By utilizing the finite blocklength regime to model the achievable data rate, the study introduces a perturbation-based iterative algorithm. The study in [18] introduces a NOMA-aided UAV network designed to support integrated sensing, communication, and computation (ISCC) functionalities for next-generation wireless systems. The UAV acts as a multi-functional aerial node, enabling edge computing for users, transmitting integrated sensing and communication beams to detect targets, and offloading data to a fog node. The objective is to maximize network computation throughput while meeting quality requirements for sensing, power consumption, and URLLC. To achieve this, the authors propose a deep reinforcement learning (DRL)-based algorithm named SAC-TPBD. This algorithm dynamically adjusts UAV trajectory and beamforming based on real-time user queue backlogs and deviations in URLLC constraints, enabling URLLC-aware optimization.

Another critical consideration is energy efficiency. Given the limited energy resources of UAVs, it is essential to balance energy consumption with reliability [19]. Intelligent scheduling algorithms have been developed to optimize task assignments while minimizing energy use. Similarly, energy-aware routing protocols ensure that UAVs maintain communication reliability without depleting their power reserves prematurely, thereby extending their operational duration. The study in [20] examines the integration of UAVs into spectrum-sensing cognitive communication networks to enhance the performance of URLLC and mMTC services in 5G and beyond networks. The paper focuses on the dual requirements of these services: energy efficiency and connection probability for mMTC, and minimal latency for URLLC. In the proposed framework, a cognitive UAV acts as an aerial secondary transmitter, sharing the unlicensed spectrum with a ground base station. The study derives analytical expressions for throughput, energy efficiency, and latency for mMTC/URLLC UAV devices and formulates an optimization problem to maximize energy efficiency while satisfying URLLC latency and mMTC throughput requirements. Using the Lagrangian method and Karush-Kuhn-Tucker conditions, the algorithm jointly optimizes the transmission powers of mMTC and URLLC users. The work in [21] addresses the challenges of achieving URLLC in mission-critical applications by leveraging UAV-assisted systems for IoT networks. The paper focuses on minimizing the average uplink transmit power of IoT devices by jointly optimizing device scheduling, power control, resource allocation, and UAV deployment under the finite blocklength regime. The optimization problem, classified as a mixed-integer nonconvex problem, is tackled using an iterative algorithm based on block

coordinate descent (BCD) and Lagrange dual decomposition techniques. Analytical convergence of the algorithm is also demonstrated.

The study in [22] explores a UAV-enabled relay communication system designed to deliver latency-critical messages with ultra-high reliability using the amplifier-and-forward mode. The paper focuses on jointly optimizing UAV location and power allocation to minimize decoding error probability while ensuring strict latency constraints. The study considers two channel models: a free-space channel model and a three-dimensional (3D) channel model. For the free-space model, a low-complexity iterative algorithm is proposed, with a globally optimal solution derived for scenarios with extremely high signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). For the 3D model, another low-complexity iterative algorithm is developed to address the optimization problem effectively. The work in [23] investigates a power-efficient resource allocation scheme for URLLC systems using UAVs in 6G networks. UAVs are recognized for their dynamic positioning and line-of-sight communication capabilities, which make them suitable for URLLC applications. However, their operation is challenged by flight instability, jittering effects caused by wind, and imperfect channel state information (CSI), which can degrade communication performance. The proposed framework optimizes UAV positioning and blocklength allocation under finite blocklength constraints, imperfect CSI, and environmental disturbances. A perturbation-based semidefinite programming approach is introduced to minimize the sum power consumption. The method achieves significant power savings, up to 77.18% compared to fixed benchmark algorithms, while maintaining performance levels similar to exhaustive search methods but with lower computational complexity.

Furthermore, UAVs can be integrated seamlessly with mobile edge computing (MEC) frameworks, processing data closer to end-users to achieve ultra-low latency [24]. This adaptability makes UAVs an indispensable component of modern communication networks, capable of meeting the rigorous requirements of URLLC in various challenging environments. The study in [25] examines a UAV-enabled MEC system where ground devices offload parts of their latency-sensitive and mission-critical computational tasks to a UAV-carried MEC server, while performing the remaining computations locally. To ensure the low-latency requirements of MEC operations, URLLC is utilized for task offloading between devices and the UAV. The paper aims to minimize the maximum computation latency across all devices by jointly optimizing several parameters: computing times and CPU frequencies of the devices and UAV, offloading bandwidths of the devices, and the UAV's three-dimensional location. To solve this complex optimization problem, the study proposes a decomposition-based algorithm that breaks it into three subproblems: optimizing the UAV's horizontal location, altitude, and the offloading bandwidths and CPU frequencies. The algorithm leverages a logarithmic approximation for finite-blocklength data rate expressions and applies the successive convex approximation technique to address the non-convex nature of the problem. Additionally, a semi-closed-form solution is derived to simplify bandwidth and CPU frequency optimization. The work in [26] explores a multiagent UAV-aided MEC system designed to meet the URLLC requirements of intelligent autonomous transport applications. The MEC architecture leverages UAVs to perform task offloading and caching, ensuring QoS while addressing latency and reliability challenges. The primary objective is to minimize network energy consumption by jointly optimizing communication and computation parameters, including task offloading decisions, edge caching policies, uplink transmission power, and processing rates. Due to the non-convex nature and computational complexity of the optimization problem, an alternating optimization algorithm is proposed, solving caching, offloading, and power allocation in an iterative manner.

C. HABS-Based URLLC

HAPS operate in the stratosphere, leveraging their unique position to combine the benefits of both satellite and terrestrial communication systems. Positioned at altitudes between 17 and 22 kilometers, HAPS offer a versatile and cost-effective solution for bridging connectivity gaps and enhancing network performance. One of the most significant advantages of HAPS is their ability to provide large-area coverage. Unlike satellites, HAPS operate closer to the Earth's surface, which significantly reduces latency

and improves signal quality. This capability makes HAPS an ideal complement to terrestrial infrastructure, particularly in remote or underserved regions where deploying traditional communication systems is not feasible. Flexibility is another hallmark of HAPS. These systems can be rapidly deployed and reconfigured to address dynamic network requirements. For instance, in disaster recovery scenarios, HAPS can be quickly mobilized to restore connectivity and support emergency response efforts. Similarly, during large-scale events or in regions experiencing sudden surges in network demand, HAPS can provide temporary capacity boosts, ensuring uninterrupted communication services. Integration with existing communication networks is a critical feature of HAPS. Seamless interworking with terrestrial and satellite systems enables the creation of hybrid architectures that leverage the strengths of each domain. Through advanced techniques such as network slicing and multi-connectivity strategies, HAPS can prioritize URLLC traffic, ensuring the stringent requirements of mission-critical applications are met without compromising the performance of other services. HAPS also support a wide range of applications, further solidifying their role in next-generation networks. These include environmental monitoring, where HAPS platforms can gather high-resolution data over extended periods, and intelligent transportation systems, where they facilitate real-time vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication. Additionally, HAPS play a pivotal role in enabling aerial IoT networks, providing connectivity for airborne sensors and drones operating in challenging environments. Their ability to adapt to varying demands and integrate seamlessly with other network layers makes HAPS an indispensable component of future communication ecosystems.

The study in [27] explores the integration of near-space information networks (NSIN) with RIS to enhance wireless communication systems, particularly for URLLC services. By leveraging RIS to dynamically alter wireless channels, the paper addresses the challenges of achieving energy efficiency and high reliability while minimizing latency. The authors formulate a resource optimization problem that aims to maximize effective throughput and minimize power consumption under URLLC and physical resource constraints. To address the complexities of accurate channel estimation, RIS phase alignment, and solution design, the study introduces a joint resource allocation algorithm. This algorithm incorporates a channel estimation method using message passing and optimizes RIS phase shifts to boost channel gain. The problem is simplified by deriving a tractable expression for decoding error probability and decomposing it into a two-layered optimization framework. The work in [28] examines the integration of HAPS into the cell-switching framework to enhance energy efficiency and ensure sustainable and ubiquitous connectivity. The proposed approach incorporates a delay-aware strategy that respects user latency requirements, employing a best-effort method to meet these demands. To optimize cell-switching, the paper introduces a lightweight Q-learning algorithm designed to balance energy consumption and quality-of-service (QoS). The work in [29] focuses on the critical role of UAVs and HAPS in providing emergency communication solutions for areas without ground connectivity. The paper highlights how these aerial multi-layer systems can establish ad hoc coverage and ensure backhaul connectivity, especially for IoT applications in emergency scenarios. The study reviews Narrowband IoT and LoRa/LoRaWAN as key technologies, emphasizing their suitability in emergency contexts. An analytical approach is employed to compare the random-access schemes of these technologies, focusing on efficient data collection from ground IoT devices. The findings underline the importance of UAVs and HAPS in enabling reliable and efficient IoT-based communication during emergencies.

III. OPEN CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

A. Challenges

Despite promising advancements, several challenges remain in achieving the stringent requirements of URLLC in NTN:

1) Latency Optimization::

- **Propagation Delay:** Addressing the inherent delays in satellite and HAPS communication is critical for achieving the stringent latency requirements of URLLC. These delays, primarily caused by the vast distances signals must travel, can be mitigated through advanced relay techniques. Multi-hop relay

systems reduce the overall path length, while low-latency routing protocols optimize data transmission paths to minimize delays. Additionally, techniques such as caching at relay nodes and predictive routing ensure that data reaches its destination in the shortest possible time.

- **Edge Processing:** Offloading computational tasks to edge nodes, such as UAV-based and HAPS-based MEC units, is a transformative approach to reducing latency and improving responsiveness. By processing data closer to the source, edge nodes significantly decrease the time required to transmit and analyze information. This is particularly valuable in scenarios requiring real-time decision-making, such as autonomous vehicle coordination or remote surgery. The integration of AI-driven edge analytics further enhances the capability of these nodes, enabling predictive processing and adaptive workload distribution [30].
- **Network Synchronization:** Ensuring precise timing and synchronization across diverse NTN components is fundamental to maintaining low latency and high reliability. Synchronization techniques involve the use of atomic clocks and advanced timing protocols, such as Precision Time Protocol (PTP), to ensure all network elements operate in harmony. Accurate synchronization minimizes jitter and packet loss, enhancing the quality of service for URLLC applications. Furthermore, adaptive synchronization algorithms dynamically adjust timing based on network conditions, ensuring consistent performance even in highly dynamic environments.

2) *Resource Allocation:*

- **Spectrum Scarcity:** The limited availability of spectrum in NTNs is a significant challenge that necessitates innovative solutions to ensure efficient utilization. Cognitive radio technology emerges as a critical enabler in this regard, allowing dynamic spectrum sensing and allocation to maximize spectral efficiency. By leveraging machine learning algorithms, cognitive radios can identify underutilized frequency bands and adaptively allocate them to meet URLLC requirements [31]–[33]. Additionally, NOMA techniques facilitate simultaneous data transmission for multiple users within the same frequency band, significantly enhancing spectrum efficiency. These advancements are crucial for addressing the growing demand for bandwidth-intensive applications in NTNs.
- **Dynamic Allocation:** Adapting to varying traffic demands and channel conditions is vital for maintaining the stringent requirements of URLLC [34]–[40]. Reinforcement learning-based resource allocation algorithms provide a powerful framework for dynamic spectrum management [41]–[48]. These algorithms learn from network conditions and traffic patterns to optimize resource distribution in real time, ensuring that high-priority URLLC traffic receives the necessary resources without compromising the performance of other services. Dynamic allocation strategies are particularly effective in heterogeneous NTN environments, where traffic patterns and channel characteristics vary significantly across different regions and applications.
- **Cross-Layer Optimization:** Coordinating resource allocation across the physical, Medium Access Control (MAC), and application layers is essential for achieving end-to-end performance improvements in NTNs. Cross-layer optimization frameworks integrate decisions across multiple layers of the communication stack, enabling a holistic approach to resource management. For instance, adjustments at the physical layer, such as power control and modulation schemes, can be dynamically aligned with MAC-layer scheduling and application-layer QoS requirements. This coordinated approach ensures that NTN systems can meet the latency, reliability, and efficiency demands of URLLC applications, even under challenging network conditions.

3) *Reliability Assurance:*

- **Redundancy Mechanisms:** Implementing robust redundancy and failover strategies is critical to ensuring the reliability of NTNs for URLLC applications. Multi-connectivity solutions, which enable devices to connect simultaneously to multiple NTN components such as satellites, UAVs, and terrestrial systems, provide a safety net against network disruptions. In the event of a failure in one link, traffic can seamlessly switch to an alternative connection, minimizing the risk of service interruptions. Cooperative communication further enhances redundancy by enabling collaboration

between NTN nodes to share resources and distribute traffic dynamically. This approach not only ensures uninterrupted communication but also improves overall network performance by balancing loads efficiently.

- **Channel Modeling:** Developing accurate NTN-specific channel models is essential for predicting and managing the unique propagation characteristics of NTNs. Factors such as atmospheric effects, including rain attenuation and cloud scattering, significantly impact signal reliability. Similarly, multipath effects caused by reflections from various surfaces in NTN environments introduce additional complexities. Accurate modeling of these phenomena allows for the design of advanced error correction techniques and adaptive modulation schemes that ensure consistent performance. These models also enable simulation-based optimization, which aids in the deployment of robust communication systems tailored to specific NTN scenarios.
- **Predictive Analytics:** Leveraging AI for predictive analytics is a transformative approach to maintaining network reliability in NTNs. AI algorithms can analyze historical and real-time data to identify patterns indicative of potential failures. By predicting issues such as link degradation or hardware malfunctions, network operators can take proactive measures to mitigate disruptions. Predictive models also enable dynamic resource allocation and redundancy activation before failures occur, ensuring seamless operation. This capability is particularly valuable in mission-critical applications, where even minor communication interruptions can have significant consequences.

4) *Integration with Terrestrial Networks:*

- **Handover Management:** Ensuring seamless handovers between terrestrial and non-terrestrial components is a critical requirement for maintaining uninterrupted communication in hybrid networks. Predictive algorithms play a pivotal role in enabling smooth transitions by anticipating mobility patterns and preemptively allocating resources to the next network node. Low-latency signaling protocols further enhance this process by reducing the time required to execute handovers, ensuring that the stringent latency requirements of URLLC applications are met. Advanced techniques, such as AI-driven mobility management, are being explored to improve handover efficiency in highly dynamic environments, such as UAV swarms or moving vehicles in NTN-terrestrial systems.
- **Network Slicing:** Customizing network slices specifically tailored for URLLC traffic is essential to meet the diverse QoS requirements in hybrid NTN-terrestrial networks [49]. Network slicing enables the allocation of dedicated resources to mission-critical applications, ensuring consistent performance despite fluctuations in network load. By leveraging virtualization and software-defined networking (SDN) technologies, operators can dynamically adjust slices to prioritize URLLC traffic without compromising the performance of other services. This adaptability is particularly crucial in scenarios involving simultaneous support for eMBB and mMTC alongside URLLC [50]–[59].
- **Traffic Orchestration:** Optimizing traffic distribution across terrestrial and NTN segments is vital to achieving a balanced network performance and cost efficiency. Traffic orchestration frameworks utilize intelligent algorithms to dynamically route data based on factors such as network congestion, link quality, and application requirements. This ensures that high-priority URLLC traffic is directed through the most reliable and low-latency paths while offloading less critical data to alternative routes. Additionally, multi-connectivity solutions allow traffic to be split across multiple links, enhancing redundancy and reliability. As NTNs evolve, the integration of machine learning models for real-time traffic prediction and adaptive routing will further enhance the efficiency of traffic orchestration mechanisms.

5) *Security and Privacy:*

- **Lightweight Encryption:** Developing low-latency encryption protocols is critical for ensuring data integrity and confidentiality in NTNs. Traditional encryption methods often impose significant computational overhead and latency, which can be detrimental to URLLC applications requiring sub-millisecond communication. Lightweight encryption techniques, such as those based on elliptic curve cryptography (ECC) or stream ciphers, are being tailored to meet the specific constraints of NTNs

[60], [61]. These protocols focus on achieving robust security with minimal resource consumption, making them ideal for deployment in resource-constrained NTN environments, including satellites and UAVs. Furthermore, integrating quantum-resistant encryption methods offers a future-proof solution against emerging cyber threats posed by quantum computing.

- **Intrusion Detection:** Employing AI-based systems for real-time anomaly detection and threat mitigation is a transformative approach to securing NTNs. These systems utilize machine learning algorithms to monitor network behavior and identify deviations that may indicate cyber-attacks or system vulnerabilities. Real-time intrusion detection systems (IDS) are particularly valuable in NTNs, where manual oversight is often limited due to the remote and autonomous nature of these networks. Techniques such as deep learning and reinforcement learning enable IDS to adapt dynamically to evolving threats, providing a proactive defense against issues like signal jamming, spoofing, and unauthorized access. Additionally, the integration of distributed IDS across NTN nodes ensures comprehensive coverage and rapid threat response.
- **Secure Network Architectures:** Designing NTN-specific security frameworks is essential to address the unique vulnerabilities inherent in these networks, such as spoofing, jamming, and eavesdropping. These architectures incorporate multiple layers of security, including physical-layer encryption, secure routing protocols, and authentication mechanisms tailored to the characteristics of NTNs. For example, leveraging blockchain technology for decentralized authentication enhances trust and transparency across the network. Advanced techniques like directional signal transmission and frequency hopping add another layer of protection against interception and interference. By integrating these secure architectures with AI-driven management systems, NTNs can maintain robust defenses while ensuring the high reliability and low latency demanded by URLLC applications.

B. Future Directions

The convergence of emerging technologies with URLLC-NTN systems offers transformative potential, creating opportunities for unprecedented advancements in communication networks. These technologies not only enhance the capabilities of NTNs but also address the unique challenges of implementing URLLC requirements in diverse and dynamic environments. Following are the most promising key directions for future research:

1) *AI-Driven Optimization:* AI is fundamentally transforming resource management in NTNs, enabling unprecedented levels of efficiency and adaptability. By facilitating real-time optimization of resource allocation, interference management, and fault detection, AI ensures that the stringent requirements of URLLC are consistently met, even in highly dynamic and challenging network environments. AI-driven systems can predict network behavior and preemptively adjust resource usage to mitigate potential disruptions, enhancing both reliability and performance. One particularly promising application of AI in NTNs is federated learning, which enables collaborative model training across distributed nodes without compromising data privacy [62]–[70]. This decentralized approach is ideal for NTNs, where the vast geographic distribution of nodes, such as satellites, UAVs, and HAPS, makes centralized data processing impractical. By leveraging federated learning, NTNs can achieve scalable decision-making capabilities that adapt to local conditions while maintaining global coherence. These models optimize resource allocation and interference mitigation in real time, ensuring consistent QoS for mission-critical applications.

Moreover, AI facilitates intelligent fault detection and recovery mechanisms that significantly improve network reliability [71]–[75]. Machine learning models can analyze vast datasets to detect anomalies, identify the root causes of faults, and implement corrective measures before they impact network performance. This proactive approach minimizes downtime and enhances the robustness of NTN-enabled URLLC systems, making them more resilient to environmental and operational challenges. As AI continues to evolve, its integration with NTNs is expected to unlock new levels of efficiency, reliability, and scalability, cementing its role as a cornerstone of next-generation communication networks.

2) *Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces*: RIS represent a groundbreaking innovation in wireless communication, offering a paradigm shift in how signals are managed and optimized in the communication environment. These surfaces, composed of arrays of passive or active elements, can dynamically manipulate electromagnetic waves by reflecting, refracting, or scattering them to achieve desired propagation characteristics. This capability allows RIS to effectively counteract challenges such as multipath fading and signal attenuation, thereby enhancing signal strength and reliability—two critical requirements for URLLC in NTN. The application of RIS in NTNs holds immense potential. By embedding RIS within NTN architectures, it becomes possible to fine-tune signal pathways, ensuring optimal coverage and reducing latency for mission-critical applications. For instance, in satellite communication, RIS can be deployed to focus signals toward specific regions or users, improving link quality and minimizing interference. Similarly, integrating RIS into UAVs or HAPS can create dynamic and adaptive network environments capable of addressing the diverse and evolving demands of next-generation applications. Future research should delve deeper into the seamless integration of RIS with NTNs. Key areas include the development of energy-efficient RIS configurations to minimize power consumption while maintaining performance, the creation of adaptive control algorithms to dynamically adjust RIS settings based on real-time network conditions, and the exploration of advanced materials for RIS elements to enhance their functionality and durability in harsh NTN environments. By addressing these aspects, RIS can play a pivotal role in shaping the future of global connectivity, bridging gaps in coverage, and enabling NTNs to meet the stringent demands of URLLC applications.

3) *Quantum Communication*: Quantum communication offers unparalleled security and ultra-low latency, making it a groundbreaking solution for NTNs that require robust and secure data transmission. By leveraging quantum principles such as superposition and entanglement, quantum communication technologies, including quantum key distribution (QKD), provide encryption methods that are virtually immune to interception or decryption by classical computing. This level of security is critical for mission-critical applications, such as defense systems, financial transactions, and sensitive industrial operations, where data integrity and confidentiality are paramount. Entanglement-based networks further extend the capabilities of quantum communication by enabling instantaneous and highly secure data sharing between connected nodes. Such networks hold immense potential for enhancing the reliability and security of NTNs, ensuring seamless communication even under adversarial conditions. These technologies directly address growing concerns about cyber threats, especially as advances in quantum computing pose significant risks to traditional encryption methods. Hybrid quantum-classical NTN architectures present a promising and practical pathway for the near-term adoption of quantum communication. By combining the reliability and scalability of classical systems with the advanced security and ultra-low latency offered by quantum technologies, these hybrid systems achieve a balanced approach to resilience and performance. For example, quantum technologies can be integrated into the backbone of NTN infrastructures to protect critical links while classical systems handle less sensitive or latency-tolerant data. Future research should focus on overcoming technical challenges such as photon loss in free-space communication and ensuring compatibility between quantum and classical components to enable widespread deployment of quantum-enhanced NTNs.

4) *Integration with 6G Technologies*: The evolution of NTNs will be profoundly influenced by the advancements brought about by 6G technologies, which are poised to redefine the landscape of wireless communication. Among the groundbreaking features of 6G are terahertz communication, holographic beamforming, and integrated sensing and communication (ISAC). Terahertz communication unlocks ultra-high-frequency spectrums that significantly increase data rates, enabling NTNs to support data-intensive applications like real-time 8K video streaming, immersive virtual reality (VR), and advanced IoT systems. Holographic beamforming introduces a new dimension in signal control, allowing the precise shaping and direction of beams to maximize coverage, reduce interference, and enhance spectral efficiency. ISAC merges the dual functionalities of environmental sensing and data transmission, allowing NTNs to offer unprecedented capabilities in applications like autonomous navigation, disaster response, and smart city infrastructure. By combining these innovations, NTNs can achieve unparalleled performance metrics,

including higher data rates, ultra-low latency, and enhanced energy efficiency, which are vital for URLLC systems. Furthermore, the integration of 6G's native AI and edge intelligence frameworks will significantly enhance the adaptability and intelligence of NTN. AI algorithms embedded within the 6G infrastructure enable real-time resource allocation, predictive maintenance, and adaptive routing, ensuring optimal performance under dynamic network conditions. Edge intelligence further reduces latency by processing data closer to users, enabling instantaneous decision-making crucial for mission-critical applications like telemedicine, autonomous systems, and industrial automation. By leveraging these advancements, NTNs will not only meet the rigorous demands of URLLC but also drive the next wave of innovation in global connectivity, making seamless communication a reality for diverse and complex applications.

5) *Cost-Effective Solutions for Rural Deployment:* Expanding connectivity to underserved and remote regions remains a critical goal for NTNs, as it holds the potential to bridge the digital divide and bring equitable access to modern communication technologies. The vast geographical challenges in these regions, including rugged terrains, dense forests, and scattered populations, necessitate innovative approaches that go beyond traditional terrestrial infrastructure. NTNs, with their ability to provide wide-area coverage and rapid deployment, are uniquely positioned to address these issues. Developing low-cost, energy-efficient NTN components is essential to ensure that these systems can be deployed at scale without imposing prohibitive costs. Solar-powered NTN platforms represent a particularly promising innovation, enabling long-term operation in remote areas where conventional power sources are unavailable. These platforms not only reduce dependency on expensive energy logistics but also contribute to the sustainability of NTN deployments by utilizing renewable energy. Another crucial aspect is the design of simplified, low-complexity algorithms tailored for rural deployments. These algorithms prioritize essential communication functionalities while minimizing computational and energy requirements, making them ideal for environments with limited resources. For example, lightweight routing protocols and spectrum-efficient communication techniques can ensure reliable data transmission even under challenging conditions. Additionally, partnerships between governments, private sectors, and non-profit organizations are pivotal in driving large-scale implementation. By fostering collaboration, stakeholders can pool resources to subsidize deployment costs and ensure that advanced communication technologies are accessible to populations in remote areas. These collective efforts not only enhance connectivity but also unlock economic opportunities, improve access to education and healthcare, and foster global inclusivity, transforming lives and communities across the globe.

IV. CONCLUSION

The integration of URLLC with NTNs represents a groundbreaking evolution in wireless communication, extending the boundaries of connectivity and enabling seamless communication for mission-critical applications. These applications, such as autonomous systems, remote healthcare, disaster recovery, and global Industrial IoT, require unparalleled levels of reliability and minimal latency, making the role of NTNs indispensable. By addressing the inherent limitations of terrestrial networks, NTNs unlock new opportunities for global communication, particularly in remote and underserved regions where terrestrial infrastructure cannot meet these rigorous demands. This synergy creates transformative possibilities, driving innovation across multiple industries while bridging the digital divide. However, achieving the stringent requirements of URLLC in NTNs introduces a unique set of challenges that demand immediate attention and innovative solutions. One of the most pressing challenges is overcoming latency bottlenecks caused by the vast distances signals must traverse in high-altitude and orbital communication systems. Techniques such as multi-orbit constellations, edge computing integration, and advanced routing algorithms are being explored to mitigate these delays. Resource allocation presents another significant obstacle, as NTNs operate within limited spectrum availability while serving an increasing demand for high-bandwidth applications. The adoption of cognitive radio, NOMA, and AI-driven resource management algorithms offer promising pathways to optimize spectrum utilization. Overcoming these challenges requires a multidimensional approach that leverages advancements across hardware, software, and system design.

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